

Validating the Weiskopf 3x3 Data Quality Assessment Framework

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Background

- The Health Information Technology for Economic and Clinical Health Act of 2009 resulted in large-scale deployment of electronic health records (EHRs); see Figure 1.
- EHR data has allowed for significant advancement and improvement in clinical practice and research.
- EHR data violates assumptions of data quality (DQ).
- Standardized methodologies for assessing and reporting DQ anomalies have yet to be identified.

Figure 1. EHR content and processes

Jensen PB, Jensen LJ, and Brunak S. Mining electronic health records: towards better research applications and clinical care. Nature Reviews, June 2012 (13): 395-403

Objectives

The current project aimed to quantitatively validate the Weiskopf 3x3 DQ assessment framework (Figure 2) through developing operational measures for each cell in the framework.

Methods

The current study utilized a three-step validation process:

1. Data model-independent operational measure development (i.e., descriptive statistics and visualizations);
2. Implement operational measures against the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model;
3. Field-test operational measures using OMOP-compliant data collected from Children's Hospital Colorado (CHCO) between 2010-2014.

Results

- The final data set included 560,451 patients across 769,648 procedures, 3,350,801 visits, and 11,617,870 conditions.
- Operational measures and visualizations were developed for 8/9 framework cells (examples for 3/9 cells shown in Figures 3-5).
- Cell 2C in Figure 2 was unable to be operationally defined.
- Operational measures were successfully executed against the OMOP common data model; field-testing revealed several DQ anomalies.

Figure 2. Weiskopf 3x3 DQ Assessment Framework

	A: COMPLETE	B: CORRECT	C: CURRENT
1: PATIENT	1A Are there sufficient data points for each patient?	1B Is the distribution of values across patients plausible?	1C Were all data recorded during the timeframe of interest?
2: VARIABLES	2A Are there sufficient data points for each variable?	2B Is there concordance between variables?	2C Were variables recorded in the desired order?
3: TIME	3A Are there sufficient data points for each time?	3B Is the progression of data over time plausible?	3C Were data recorded with the desired regularity over time?

Weiskopf, N. G. (2014). Enabling the Reuse of Electronic Health Record Data through Data Quality Assessment and Transparency. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Columbia University, NY.

Figure 3. Correctness: Patient (1B)

Patient Year of Birth Distribution

The box plot in this figure illustrates all patients were born between 1909 and 2014 ($M=2003.36$, $SD=8.20$).

DQ Finding: Of the 560,451 patients, (0.10%) were born prior to 1940. This is inconsistent with CHCO records.

Figure 4. Correctness: Variable (2B)

This figure illustrates the temporal ordering of visit occurrence observations by place of service.

DQ Finding: The Ambulatory Surgery, Inpatient, and Outpatient Departments had erroneous observations where the visit start timestamp occurred after the visit end timestamp.

Figure 5. Correctness: Time (3B)

This figure illustrates the trends in monthly visits to the Emergency Department (ER) by year.

DQ Finding: The counts of December ER visits were significantly lower in both 2010 and 2011 ($p < .001$) compared to 2012-2014.

Recommendations

- Understanding the usability of EHR data is of paramount importance.
- The Current Variable cell (2C) of the framework requires operational measure development.
- Analysis-driven validation efforts utilizing alternative data sources are still needed.
- Framework-based applications and tool development is crucial for adoptability.